

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.	B492		
Date:	01 DEC 2009		
Take Off:	13:36:13Z	Z	Z
Landing:	16:35:56Z	Z	Z
Flight Time:	2h 59m 43s	h m s	h m s

Campaign: CIMS

Operating Area: Weybourne and East Coast

POB Position	Name	Institute
1 Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2 Co	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3 CCM	Robbie Voaden	Directflight
4 Mission Scientist	Gavin McMeeking	Manchester
5 Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6 Core Chemistry / WAS 1	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7 Core Chemistry / WAS 2	Axel Wellpot	FAAM
8 CIMS	Michael Le Breton	Manchester
9 QCLAS / Cloud Physics	James Dorsey	Manchester
10 AMS	Will Morgan	Manchester
11 Mission Scientist Training	Carl Percival	Manchester
12		
13		
14		
15		
16		
17		
18		
19		

	Log Sheet included
Y	Flight Folder Front Page
Y	Flight Summary
Y	Met Office 0600 UTC Actual Surface analysis (ASXX) chart
Y	Track Plot (GIN or GPS)
Y	DFLFliteStar planned track
Y	Brief
	Mission Scientist 1's logs
	Mission Scientist 2's logs
	De-brief
Y	ViRC chat log
Y	Flight Manager's Instrument Status log
Y	Flight Manager's Faults/Incidents log
	Pre-flight log
	Core Chemistry / NOx / TDLAS
	Cloud Physics In Flight
	Cloud Physics Processing
	AVAPS
	PSAP log
	Filters
	Printed Plots
	Screengrabs
	Planning charts or plots
	Images Emailed To BAe146 In Flight

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	2009-11-05	Alan Woolley	Initial version
R1			
r2			

Sortie Brief: CIMS 2a**Flight Number : B493****Date: Tuesday 1st December 2009****Mission Scientist: Gavin McMeeking****CIMS Sortie Aims:**

To study the evolution of ammonia in a plume as it advects away from the source. To investigate the operation of the CIMS, QCLAS instruments.

CIMS Scientific Aims

1. To investigate the ammonia budget along the east coast of the UK and the evolution of an agriculture plume as it is advected away from the source.
2. To test the operation of the CIMS.
3. To test the operation of the QCLAS.
4. To investigate the role of ammonia in controlling inorganic aerosol formation.

CIMS Weather Conditions

Ideally, westerlies coming from the main sources of urban/rural ammonia.

CIMS Sortie Location:

The plan is to fly across plumes originating from agricultural sources. On this occasion the focus will be to head to the north east coast of the UK to sample a variety of plumes from heavily agricultural East Anglia to urban/industrial Tyneside/Teesside.

CIMS Sortie Detail:

1. Take off and climb to FL 100 for transit at cruise speed to AMPEP way point 86
Perform a profile ascent from 50 feet to 5,000 feet to determine height of boundary layer, this expected to be between 2,000 and 4,000 feet. Mission scientist will chose altitude to fly along AMPEP points down to AMPEP way point 42 points. i.e. 38 – 86 – 40 – 41 – 42
2. Turn and fly along AMPEP way points anti clockwise direction along along the following way points – 41 – 40 – 86 – 87 – 80 – 79 – 78 – 77. Altitude should be altered if below minimum altitude for night flying after sunset
3. Turn and fly along the following way points – 78 – 79 – 80 – 87 – 86 – 38 then land at Cranfield.

Sortie Brief: CIMS 2

CIMS Key Measurements requiring operator intervention during flight

Cloud Physics

- **PCASP**, Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest e.g. high/low concentrations,
- .

Chemistry Measurements

CO, TECO NO_x, Ozone, SO₂ to operate continuously.

AMS - to be operated on **Rosemount inlet** out of cloud, **CVI** inlet in cloud. The inlet should be kept closed to avoid contamination whilst the GPU is operating prior to takeoff. It may be opened once the GPU has been removed or after take-off. Similarly, intake should be closed before GPU is started post-flight or before landing.

Video – the default recording setup should be forward and rearward facing.

asxx 02/12/2009 12:00 UTC

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B492

Date: 01 December

Project: CIMS

Location: Weybourne and E Coast

Start End

Time	Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
070728		Start-Up	0.06 kft	051	52'12.56N, 0'10.45E
133109		ASP	0.09 kft	137	Open
133613		T/O	3.1 kft	332	Cambridge
134258	135413	Run 1	10.0 kft	045	NOx Cal
140253	140645	Run 2	0.17 - 0.14 kft	273	100', Q1012mb, OE-OW
140505		Event	0.12 kft	284	50' abeam WAO
141130	141730	Run 3	0.84 kft	100	800', end at OE
141219			0.86 kft	102	Ovhd OW
141428		Event	0.86 kft	109	Abeam WAO
142046	142525	Run 4	1.4 kft	289	1300' OW
142200			1.4 kft	282	At OE
142400		Heimann	1.4 kft	282	Cal
142418		Event	1.4 kft	282	Abeam WAO
142909	143342	Run 5	1.4 - 1.3 kft	191	1300', ON-LS
143112		Event	1.4 kft	191	Ovhd WAO
143136		Event	1.4 kft	192	WAS filling (not successful)
143857		WAS	1.4 kft	093	Case 7 - Pump not on!!
144302	152040	Run 6	0.59 - 0.56 kft	169	500', WP40 500'-1.4k'
144552		Heimann	0.58 kft	180	Cal
145956			0.57 kft	178	WP41
151429			0.64 kft	202	WP42
152040	152156	Profile 1	0.56 - 1.5 kft	012	500'-1.4k'
152156	154214	Run 7	1.5 - 1.4 kft	013	
152955		Event	1.4 kft	015	decend 100'
153008		Event	1.4 kft	013	WP41
153743		Event	1.4 kft	315	Over land
154705	154951	Profile 2	2.1 - 0.23 kft	078	2.0k'-50', Norwich missed approach
155050			1.00 kft	090	Q1011
155755	160112	Run 8	0.66 - 0.63 kft	280	500'
155946		Event	0.61	289	Abeam WAO
160105			0.61 kft	277	WP87
160514	162406	Run 9	10.0 - 7.8 kft	090	NOx Cal
161500		Video	10.0 kft	238	Stop Recording
163556		Land	0.46 kft	246	Cranfield
163818		ASP	0.45 kft	233	Closed
164025		Shutdown	0.46 kft	303	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B492

Date: 01 Dec 09

Instruments

1. Nevz TWC zeros okay but signal output always flatlines (at 0uA on control unit meter). DLU reading always 6346 DRSU.
2. Video – no signal at Video laptop. Tried cycling power to digitiser box several times, no improvement. Removed aircraft Ethernet cable connections and fitted flying leads, then it worked!
3. Ethernet Hub at SSP 3, possible u/s socket on hub, port 3 (3rd from front face).
4. Printer – error on FM pc when try to print – no connection.
5. FM PC – error messages ref LAN5 – limited or no connectivity
6. Video recording – crashed after ~1hr
7. WAS – pump not switched on so no bottles filled (Case 7)
8. Core Chem laptop – TCPIP conflict with Mission Scientist 1. CC address, changed to .211

Aircraft

1. Icing – delay take-off (Cambridge deicing kit u/s)

Satcom

MPDS –

Satcom H –

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Choose A Flight Number To Show Instrument Status For It

Choose Flight

[back](#)

Key :

	Not Operated		
	Minor Problems		
	Ok		

B492

Primary Systems

- AMTG
- AVAPS
- Cabin Pressure Rmount
- Camera - Downward Facing
- Camera - Forward Facing
- Camera - Rearward Facing
- Camera - Upward Facing
- Cruciform GPS
- DLU AERACK
- DLU BBR Lower
- DLU BBR Upper
- DLU Core Chem
- DLU Core Consoles
- DLU Port Aft
- DLU Port Fwd
- DLU Stbd Fwd
- Fax machine
- GIN Applanix POSAV510
- HORACE
- INU Honeywell H423
- Printer
- Radar Altimeter
- RVSM IAS
- RVSM Static Pressure
- S9 Static Press Rmount
- Satcom Phones
- Satcom Data
- Turb Diff Centre-Static
- Turb Diff Left-Right
- Turb Diff Up-Down
- Turb Horizontal Check
- Turb Vertical Check
- Weather Radar
- XR5 GPS

Temperature

- Cabin Temperature
- Heimann
- Rosemount DIT
- Rosemount NDIT
- Hygrometry**
- Buck CR2
- FWVS
- General Eastern
- Total Water Probe
- SAW Hygrometer

Remote Sensing

- BBR (clear) Lower
- BBR (clear) Upper
- BBR (IR) Lower
- BBR (IR) Upper
- BBR (red) Lower
- BBR (red) Upper
- ARIES
- CASI/ATM
- DEIMOS
- IR Camera
- JNO2 Photometer Lower
- JNO2 Photometer Upper
- JO1D Photometer Lower
- JO1D Photometer Upper
- LIDAR
- MARSS
- Mini-LIDAR
- SHIMS Lower
- SHIMS Upper
- SWS
- TAFTS

Cloud Physics

- 2DC
- 2DP
- FFSSP
- Johnson Williams
- Nevzorov
- 2DS
- ADA
- CAPS
- CDP (Canister)
- CDP (Fuselage)
- CIP 100
- CIP 25
- CPI
- INC
- SID1
- SID2
- SID3

Aerosol

- CPC 3025A
- CPC 3786 H2O
- Filters 47mm
- Filters 90mm
- Nephelometer - Dry
- Nephelometer - Wet
- PCASP
- PCASP SPP-200
- PSAP
- AMS
- CCN
- CPC 3010A
- CPC (AMS)
- CVI Inlet
- CVI PCASP-X
- CVI Ly-A Hygro
- LTI
- SMPS
- SP2
- UHSAS
- VACC

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002
- NOx TE42C
- Ozone TE49
- Ozone TE49C
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4 channel
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2 channel
- CIMS
- FAGE
- Formaldehyde
- NOx FAAM
- NOxy
- ORAC
- PAN
- PERCA
- Peroxide
- PTRMS
- QCL
- SO2 TE43C
- TDLAS (1C)
- WAS Bags
- WAS Bottles

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- QCL
- SO2 TE43C
- TDLAS (1C)
- WAS Bags
- WAS Bottles

Flight B492 vIRC log

** FAAMOpsCranfiel (FAAMOpsBas@i.love.debian.org) has joined #faam146

<wao> Hi. Brian at wao. tel no 01263 588154

<wao> Wao conditions good Northerly flow, 5m/s wind speed , good visibility

[FAAMOpsCranfiel] Should get the results from a meeting at Cambridge shortly - seem to have a problem with icing there (whether airframe or runway I'm not sure right now)

[FAAMOpsCranfiel] (So not airborne just yet)

<wao> thanks Brian

[FAAMOpsCranfiel] (0850) Latest: still unable to fly due to ice on wings and fuel at -2deg.C. Brian, expect a call from Mo Smith about now.

<wao> Chatted to Mo. Thanks for updates. Much welcomed

*** wao (waofaam@i.love.debian.org) has quit IRC [Quit: User pushed the X - because it's Xtra, baby]

[FAAMOpsCranfiel] (0926) No flight tomorrow, waiting on results from a meeting at Cambridge at 0930 to see how things are over there.

*** wao (waofaam@i.love.debian.org) has joined #faam146

*** wao (waofaam@i.love.debian.org) has quit IRC [Quit: User pushed the X - because it's Xtra, baby]

*** wao (waofaam@i.love.debian.org) has joined #faam146

<wao> any news?

*** wao (waofaam@i.love.debian.org) has quit IRC [Quit: User pushed the X - because it's Xtra, baby]

[FAAMOpsCranfiel] (1346) Aircraft appears to be airborne.

*** FAAM_flt_man (GLUXE@i.love.debian.org) has joined #faam146

<FAAM_flt_man> Are you on chat now Alison?

[FAAMOpsCranfiel] Yes.

<FAAM_flt_man> I missed the last part of your satcom c message. you need to keep the lines of

<FAAM_flt_man> text short as otherwise they disappear of the screen at this end

<FAAM_flt_man> I got up to "as we... Can you let me know what came after that please?

[FAAMOpsCranfiel] sorry, was nothing urgent, just that I'm watching, not GG

<FAAM_flt_man> no problem

[FAAMOpsCranfiel] sounds like you've had a fun morning!

<FAAM_flt_man> Finally things are settling down after another lively morning!

<FAAM_flt_man> Watching paint drying has nothing on watching ice melt

<FAAM_flt_man> For info Alison, I agreed to GO purchasing breakfast for this morning's crew as we

<FAAM_flt_man> left the hotel before they started serving

[FAAMOpsCranfiel] No problem. Makes sense.

[FAAMOpsCranfiel] Does Steve C know what time to be at CFD this evening?

<FAAM_flt_man> He was leaving Camb just as we were and returning to Cfd.
<FAAM_flt_man> Is it still the plan for the Manchester guys to use this car to rtn to Camb post flight?
[FAAMOpsCranfiel] Yes.
<FAAM_flt_man> Good. That's about the only thing that hasn't changed today.
[FAAMOpsCranfiel] We may have beaten our own PB this time, not 1 booking unchanged/cancelled!
<FAAM_flt_man> Can you let Alan K know that BBCEAS rack due to be fitted on Friday please? If flying Fri, then Monday am.
[FAAMOpsCranfiel] Have done.
<FAAM_flt_man> Ta
[FAAMOpsCranfiel] Steve C is back and has left keys for MPV on his desk for Manch team.
<FAAM_flt_man> Okay, I'll let them know. And just to confirm, the key should be dropped off at the Cambridge security gate?
[FAAMOpsCranfiel] Yep. I've said by 10pm, but a bit later shouldn't make any difference.
<FAAM_flt_man> Okay
[FAAMOpsCranfiel] Have had a call from CAe re. a tour (?) of the a/c tomorrow. Are you aware of this?
<FAAM_flt_man> I had a request from Rachel Lear at the Met Office asking if the a/c would be on the ground tomorrow. I think its to do with the Boeing visit/meetings, but left it with Gg.
[FAAMOpsCranfiel] OK, will pass onto him.
<FAAM_flt_man> On yesterday's flight i tested the satcom phone and got Steve D to phone the a/c. both calls worked. it will be interesting to see when/where/if we get billed for this (SatcomH)
[FAAMOpsCranfiel] Interesting. I think we need to check that everyone has the right no, as I think mines wrong.
<FAAM_flt_man> I'll get the no. Steve used yesterday and circulate
<FAAM_flt_man> We are going to cut the flight short as wind / pollution conditions not good, ETA to follow
[FAAMOpsCranfiel] OK, keep me posted & I'll inform Avalon / DFL.
<FAAM_flt_man> ETA Cranfield 1645
[FAAMOpsCranfiel] I'm guessing that's local? AK asked if you've been receiving weather, as it's not showing on Satcom.
<FAAM_flt_man> No weather received. Local and Z times are the same at the moment
[FAAMOpsCranfiel] Oops!
<FAAM_flt_man> Weather message just arrived!
[FAAMOpsCranfiel] Sounds like Satcom is VERY slow today.
<FAAM_flt_man> only that one message came in, sent at 1558
[FAAMOpsCranfiel] Will check if that was the only one..
<FAAM_flt_man> Signing off now, we are on our way down, see you in a wee while.
*** FAAM_flt_man (GLUXE@i.love.debian.org) has left #faam146
*** TechMan (vircuser@i.love.debian.org) has joined

Flight B492 Satcom messages

To G-LUXE at 30 November 2009, 16:03

last posn rcd 1544

EGSC 301520Z 33009KT 270V020 9999 FEW018 SCT033 06/03 Q1002

EGSC 301405Z 3015/3021 33011KT 9999 SCT035

PROB30

TEMPO 3015/3017 35015G25KT

EGNX 301550Z 32011KT 9999 FEW035 SCT045 05/01 Q1006

EGNX 301059Z 3012/0112 34014KT 9999 SCT025

PROB30

TEMPO 3012/3017 35018G32KT

BECMG 3021/3024 VRB04KT

PROB30 0103/0109 4000 BR

BECMG 0109/0112 17010KT

EGGW 301550Z 34014KT 9999 SCT029 05/02 Q1003

EGGW 301103Z 3012/0112 01015KT 9999 SCT030

PROB40

TEMPO 3012/3018 01018G30KT

PROB30

TEMPO 3012/3014 9000 -SHRA

BECMG 0101/0104 34005KT

PROB40 0101/0110 2000 BR

EGSS 301550Z 33011KT 9999 -SHRA FEW014 BKN026 05/03 Q1002

EGSS 301103Z 3012/0118 36014KT 9999 SCT015

PROB40

TEMPO 3012/3018 36018G30KT

PROB30

TEMPO 3012/3014 9000 -SHRA BKN014

BECMG 0101/0104 34005KT

PROB40 0101/0110 3000 BR
BECMG 0115/0118 18010KT
sent 1600 pc

To G-LUXE at 30 November 2009, 16:24

Mo, Have you spoken to James Dorsey? Do I need to?
Alison

From G-LUXE at 30 November 2009, 16:49

Q aepe@faam.ac.uk
From: G-LUXE 30/11/09 1644Z
To: Alison
Hi,
No I haven't but I believe Guy has. It would be
useful to get an update of any changes to the crew
list and timings (if there have been any since this morning).
chrs
Mo

To G-LUXE at 30 November 2009, 16:54

For Mo

No changes to timings for tomorrow.

James Dorsey added to first flight.

All else remains the same so far.

G?

1655 Monday 31 November.

To G-LUXE at 30 November 2009, 16:59

last posn rcd 1645
EGSC 301620Z 33013G24KT 260V030 9999 FEW036 SCT049 06/02 Q1003

EGSC 301405Z 3015/3021 33011KT 9999 SCT035
PROB30
TEMPO 3015/3017 35015G25KT
EGGW 301650Z 34014KT 9999 -SHRA BKN041 05/02 Q1004

EGGW 301103Z 3012/0112 01015KT 9999 SCT030
PROB40
TEMPO 3012/3018 01018G30KT
PROB30
TEMPO 3012/3014 9000 -SHRA
BECMG 0101/0104 34005KT
PROB40 0101/0110 2000 BR
EGNX 301650Z 32009KT 9999 FEW025 04/00 Q1007

EGNX 301059Z 3012/0112 34014KT 9999 SCT025
PROB30
TEMPO 3012/3017 35018G32KT
BECMG 3021/3024 VRB04KT
PROB30 0103/0109 4000 BR
BECMG 0109/0112 17010KT
sent 1700 pc

From G-LUXE at 30 November 2009, 17:31

Q guat@faam.ac.uk
From: G-LUXE 30/11/09 1725Z
To: Guy

Thks Guy. V good flight so far. O3 up to 140ppb and dare
I say Buck workingdown to -70C.
chrs
Mo

To G-LUXE at 30 November 2009, 17:47

latest posn rcd 1735
EGSC 301720Z 32011KT 260V030 9999 FEW036 SCT049 05/03 Q1004

EGSC 301703Z 3018/3021 32009KT 9999 FEW040
EGGW 301720Z 35014KT 9999 FEW030 SCT044 04/02 Q1005

EGGW 301702Z 3018/0118 34009KT 9999 SCT035
PROB30 0101/0110 2000 BR
BECMG 0115/0118 18010KT
EGNX 301720Z 33010KT 9999 FEW025 04/01 Q1007

EGNX 301658Z 3018/0118 33010KT 9999 FEW025
BECMG 3021/3024 VRB04KT
PROB30 0103/0109 4000 BR
BECMG 0110/0113 16010KT

sent 1745 pc

From G-LUXE at 30 November 2009, 18:01

S
UZUK80 EGRR 301752
XXAA 8017/ 99524 70040 18124 99002 05050 ///// 88999 77999
31313 09608 81652
51515 10190 00553
61616 FAAM THAW B491 OB 01
62626 SPL 5234N00398W 1702 AEV 20504 =
XXBB 80178 99524 70040 18124 00002 05050 11001 44359
21212 00002 ///// 11001 34597
31313 09608 81652
51515 10190 00553
61616 FAAM THAW B491 OB 01
62626 SPL 5234N00398W 1702 AEV 20504 =

From G-LUXE at 30 November 2009, 18:08

Q peter.chappell@directflight.co.uk
From: G-LUXE 30/11/09 1806Z
To: Peter
ETA 1840

From G-LUXE at 01 December 2009, 05:47

G
From: Test B492 011209 01/12/09 0545Z
To: Flight Manager

To G-LUXE at 01 December 2009, 05:47

From: Test B492 011209 01/12/09 0545Z
To: Flight Manager

From G-LUXE at 01 December 2009, 07:07

Q guat@faam.ac.uk
From: G-LUXE 01/12/09 0705Z
To:

Hi Guy,

T/O delayed due to icing. Will meet at 0830 to reassess conditions.

chrs
Mo

To G-LUXE at 01 December 2009, 07:51

Thanks Mo.

I'm here as and when needed.

Guy.

From G-LUXE at 01 December 2009, 12:57

Q guat@faam.ac.uk
From: G-LUXE 01/12/09 1252Z
To: Guy

Hello Guy

Just to confirm we are going for a CIMS flight,
T/O at 1400 with a few runs over WAO at the start.
ETA Crnfd 1840, power required for 1 hour post landing
chrs
Mo

To G-LUXE at 01 December 2009, 13:41

Thanks Mo,

Will sort stuff this end.

G?

From: snoopy@metoffice.gov.uk [snoopy@metoffice.gov.uk]
Sent: 01 December 2009 12:58
To: Gratton, Guy B
Subject: Message from G-LUXE 00176

From: G-LUXE 01/12/09 1252Z
To: Guy

Hello Guy

Just to confirm we are going for a CIMS flight,
T/O at 1400 with a few runs over WAO at the start.
ETA Crnfd 1840, power required for 1 hour post landing
chrs
Mo

To G-LUXE at 01 December 2009, 13:50

Mo,
I will be flight watching this pm, as GG in mtgs. Will be on x-chat (?) as well.

Alison

To G-LUXE at 01 December 2009, 15:58

1545Z 52?37.1N 0?59E
EGTC 011550Z 16004KT CAVOK 03/01 Q1009
EGNX 011550Z 15010KT CAVOK 05/M00 Q1008
EGGW 011550Z 18003KT CAVOK 04/02 Q1010
EGSS 011550Z 18003KT 9999 SCT035 04/02 Q1010
Sent 1558
?

Last changed 01 December 2009, 15:59Z

Flight B492 – Flight Track

Flight B492 – position reports

Date/Time	Latitude	Longitude	Altitude
01/12/09 1336Z	52°12.4N	0°10.8E	219 ft
01/12/09 1340Z	52°15.7N	0°1W	4534 ft
01/12/09 1345Z	52°32N	0°22.1E	9885 ft
01/12/09 1350Z	52°49.5N	0°43.5E	9869 ft
01/12/09 1355Z	53°4.2N	1°6.8E	8786 ft
01/12/09 1400Z	52°55.3N	1°31E	1670 ft
01/12/09 1406Z	53°1.4N	0°56.7E	403 ft
01/12/09 1416Z	52°56.8N	1°21.8E	951 ft
01/12/09 1426Z	53°2.2N	0°58.8E	1423 ft
01/12/09 1434Z	52°46.4N	1°6.3E	1430 ft
01/12/09 1438Z	52°47.8N	1°25.4E	1466 ft
01/12/09 1441Z	52°52.1N	1°43.8E	767 ft
01/12/09 1449Z	52°29.1N	1°48.3E	646 ft
01/12/09 1456Z	52°5.5N	1°47.6E	666 ft
01/12/09 1500Z	51°52.9N	1°46.3E	705 ft
01/12/09 1505Z	51°36.6N	1°40.4E	666 ft
01/12/09 1510Z	51°19.9N	1°34.7E	649 ft
01/12/09 1515Z	51°3.2N	1°28.7E	738 ft
01/12/09 1520Z	51°16.7N	1°34.4E	659 ft
01/12/09 1525Z	51°34.4N	1°40.5E	1548 ft
01/12/09 1529Z	51°51.6N	1°46.5E	1473 ft
01/12/09 1537Z	52°14.2N	1°20.6E	1456 ft
01/12/09 1540Z	52°24.9N	1°6.1E	1453 ft
01/12/09 1545Z	52°37.1N	0°59E	2204 ft
01/12/09 1550Z	52°40.5N	1°16.8E	390 ft

01/12/09 1554Z	52°50.9N	1°31.8E	1453 ft
01/12/09 1601Z	53°0.5N	0°57.9E	748 ft
01/12/09 1608Z	53°3.2N	1°22.8E	9839 ft
01/12/09 1611Z	52°57.1N	1°5.8E	9856 ft
01/12/09 1615Z	52°47.3N	0°48.2E	9862 ft
01/12/09 1622Z	52°30.5N	0°9.4E	9213 ft
01/12/09 1626Z	52°24.3N	0°10.1W	5672 ft
01/12/09 1630Z	52°16.2N	0°25W	2654 ft
01/12/09 1636Z	52°4.1N	0°37.2W	515 ft

B492 05:39:57-16:41:34

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

(Lisbon) Lisboa

Badajoz

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Pointer 38°13'12.08" N 8°05'51.00" W elev 368 ft Streaming 100% Eye alt 42.02 mi

